

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu Adiyatma Taopikul Hadi¹, Alfisahrin²

Faculty Of Social and General Education, Universitas BIMA International MFH Mataram

E-mail: laluadiyatma93@gmail.com¹, alvinsa084@gmail.com²

Received : 20 January 2026

Accepted : 25 February 2026

Revised : 01 February 2026

Published : 09 March 2026

Abstract

This study compares product profit margins between the domestic and export markets of UMKM in Central Lombok. The analysis shows an average domestic margin of 5% (n=10, standard deviation 3%), while the export margin is significantly higher at 32% (n=1, standard deviation 5%). A t-test demonstrated a significant difference in margins (p-value <0.05). The export process requires more raw materials, but the profit potential is much greater. These findings can serve as a reference for UMKM in determining optimal candlenut marketing strategies. This is a comparative descriptive study using a quantitative approach. The study was conducted in Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. Data were obtained through structured interviews with UMKM to obtain information on production processes, pricing, marketing strategies, and profit margin calculations. A questionnaire was used to obtain data on production costs, selling prices, sales volumes, and profit margins.

Keywords: *Candlenut; UMKM; Domestic Market; Export; Profit Margin.*

INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (UMKM) play a strategic role in supporting the regional economy. One of the mainstay commodities of UMKM is processed candlenut products, whether in the form of peeled candlenut kernels, candlenut oil, or derivative products. Candlenuts are not only known as a key ingredient in the culinary and cosmetics industries, but also have broad market potential, both domestically and in export markets. Therefore, managing prices and profit margins from candlenut product sales is crucial to ensuring the sustainability of UMKM businesses. Furthermore, in the current era of global trade, access to export markets is more widely available to UMKM. However, not all UMKM have an adequate understanding of the risks, additional costs, and challenges faced in the export process. On the other hand, the domestic market offers ease of distribution and access, but with intense price competition. Therefore, a study of profit margins in these two markets will provide an objective picture of the potential and challenges of each.

The main problem in this research lies in the gap in information and strategies in determining profit margins between candlenut sales in the domestic and export markets. UMKM set selling prices solely based on intuition or following local market prices without considering cost structures and more optimal margin opportunities. This unclear information regarding profit comparisons results in ineffective business decisions and has the potential to hinder business growth. This research is based on initial observations that UMKM in Central Lombok still employ traditional pricing systems, without adequate market analysis. This results in suboptimal profit margins for both the domestic and export markets. This comparative study is expected to provide businesses with accurate data and information to more rationally set candlenut product prices. The research aims to identify factors influencing differences in profit margins between the domestic and export markets. These factors include production costs, packaging costs, shipping costs, customs tariffs, market demand, and consumer preferences. By understanding these factors, UMKM are expected to be able to formulate appropriate strategies in determining the selling price of candlenut products according to the target market segmentation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Margin is the percentage of profit from a product or service sold. Margin is calculated by dividing profit by capital, then divided by 100 percent. However, often the definition of margin is simpler without a percentage,

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfisahrin

namely in the form of profit, namely the difference between the selling price of goods and the capital spent to produce or purchase the goods. Another name for margin is profit, namely the difference between sales and costs incurred (cost). Margin itself is very important in company strategy. Company management will usually determine margins with several considerations that will later determine how the goods are sold, how they are marketed, how much they cost, how much they will produce, and so on.

Selling price is the amount of compensation (money or goods) required to obtain a combination of goods or services. Companies always set prices for their products in the hope that they will sell well and maximize profits. Hansen and Mowen (2001) define "selling price as the monetary amount charged by a business unit to buyers or customers for goods or services sold or delivered." According to Mulyadi (2001), "in principle, the selling price must cover full costs plus a reasonable profit. The selling price is equal to the cost of production plus a markup." From the above definition, it can be concluded that the selling price is the sum of the costs incurred by a company to produce a good or service plus the company's desired profit percentage. Therefore, to achieve the desired profit, one way for companies to attract consumers is by determining the right price for the product being sold. The right price is one that matches the quality of the product and provides customer satisfaction.

Production costs are the accumulated expenses required by a company to process raw materials into products. In other words, the total costs incurred in the production process are called production costs. According to Kuswadi (2005), production costs are costs related to calculating the cost of goods manufactured or the cost of goods sold. These costs include various costs, such as labor costs, raw materials costs, and factory overhead. Production costs are the costs incurred by a company to produce goods or finished products until those goods are ready to be marketed or sold.

METHOD

This research is a comparative descriptive study using a quantitative approach. Descriptive research aims to provide a systematic, factual, and accurate overview of the profit margins of candlenut product sales. Data collected includes information on the cost of production, selling price, sales volume, and various cost components incurred by UMKM in Central Lombok. This data will be analyzed using quantitative descriptive methods, so that the results of this study can provide a clear and measurable picture of the differences in profit margins between candlenut sales in the domestic and export markets for UMKM. This research was conducted in Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province, specifically in MSME centers engaged in the candlenut production and sales sector. This location was selected based on the region's significant candlenut commodity potential and the export activities of some UMKM. The study period is planned for three months, from May to September 2025. The population in this study is all UMKM in Central Lombok Regency who produce and market candlenut products, both for the domestic and export markets.

The sampling technique used purposive sampling with the following criteria: UMKM that have been producing and selling candlenut products for at least two years, UMKM that have accounting data related to production costs and selling prices, and UMKM that sell candlenut products in both the domestic and export markets. Based on these criteria, the planned sample size was 20 UMKM, consisting of 10 UMKM focused on the domestic market and 10 UMKM with access to the export market. Data for this study was obtained through several techniques: structured interviews were conducted with MSME respondents to obtain information on production processes, pricing, marketing strategies, and profit margin calculations. A questionnaire was developed to obtain quantitative data on production costs, selling prices, sales volume, and profit margins from each respondent. Documentation studies were conducted to collect secondary data such as production reports, sales data, export data, and local government policies related to MSME development and candlenut product exports. Field observations were conducted to directly observe the production processes, business management, and marketing systems implemented by UMKM.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfisahrin

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Production Process Data for Boiled Candlenuts (Domestic Market) and Peeled Candlenuts (Export Market)

No	Kemiri Rebus (Domestik)			Kemiri Kupas (Ekspor)		
	Proses Produksi	Waktu	Alat	Proses Produksi	Waktu	Alat
1	Cuci Bahan Baku	30 - 60 Menit	Manual	Cuci Bahan Baku	30 - 60 Menit	Manual
2	Rebus Bahan Baku	60 - 90 Menit	Manual	Oven (Jemur)	1 - 3 Hari	Sinar Matahari
3	Pendinginan	30 - 60 Menit	Manual	Pendinginan	12 - 24 Jam	Mesin
4	Sortir	-	Manual	Healer	30 - 60 Menit	Mesin
5	Oven (Pengeringan)	12 - 14 Jam	Mesin & Manual	Ayak (Filter)	15 - 30 Menit	Mesin
6	Packing	-	Manual	Sortir		Manual
7				Pengemasan		Manual
8				Vacum		Mesin
9				Labeling		Manual
10				Sealer		Mesin
11				Packing		Manual & Mesin

The table above is a summary of data from interviews with candlenut processing UMKM in Pancor Dao, Central Lombok. The data above shows the production process of boiled candlenuts for the domestic market and peeled candlenuts for the export market. Based on the data in the table above, it shows that the production process of candlenuts for the export market has a longer production process compared to boiled candlenuts for the domestic market. Each respondent or resource person explained that the process of peeled candlenut products for the export market has at least 11 stages of production processes, while boiled candlenuts have 6 stages of production processes.

Table 2

Data on Raw Material Requirements for Boiled Candlenuts (Domestic Market) and Peeled Candlenuts (Export Market)

Jenis Produk	Target Produksi	Satuan	Isi (35%)		Kulit (60%)	Error (5%)	Kebutuhan Bahan Baku	KET
			Utuh (70%)	Keping (30%)	Gangkang	Foder (Debu)		
Kemiri Rebus (Domestik)	1	Kg	0,70	0,30	1,71	0,14	2,86	kemiri rebus dengan pasar domestik menerima produksi custom baik itu kemiri utuh dan keping
Kemiri Kupas (Ekspor)	1	Kg	1,00	0,43	2,45	0,20	4,08	kemiri kupas dengan pasar ekspor hanya menerima produksi berupa kemiri utuh

The table above shows that to produce 1 kg of candlenut from the boiling process only requires 2.86 kg of raw materials of candlenut logs, while to produce 1 kg of peeled candlenut for the export market requires 4.08 kg of raw materials of candlenut logs. The difference in raw material requirements is because the export market only accepts products in whole form without breaking or shards, so to produce 1 kg of whole candlenut requires more raw materials than boiled candlenut whose market accepts custom candlenut products, namely whole candlenuts with shards. From the data above it also shows that each production process of raw materials of candlenut logs processed by UMKM in Central Lombok will be 4 parts, namely (1) Shell (skin), (2) whole candlenut, (3) Candlenut shards, (4) foder (dust) / Shrinkage / Error.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfisahrin

Tabel 3

Average Data on Raw Material Prices and Labor Costs between Boiled Candlenut Products (Domestic Market) and Peeled Candlenut Products (Export Market)

No	Kemiri Rebus (Domestik)			Kemiri Kupas (Ekspor)		
	Uraian	Biaya Tenaga Kerja	KET	Uraian	Biaya Tenaga Kerja	KET
1	Harga Bahan Baku	Rp. 9.500 s/d 12.000	Rata-rata Harga kemiri Gelondongan /Kg dalam 6 bulan Terakhir (Rp. 9.500, 11.000, dan 12.000) atau rata-rata Rp. 10.833/kg	Harga Bahan Baku	Rp. 9.500 s/d 12.000	Rata-rata Harga kemiri Gelondongan /Kg dalam 6 bulan Terakhir (Rp. 9.500, 11.000, dan 12.000)
2	Cuci Bahan Baku Rebus Bahan Baku Pendinginan - -	Rp. 180.000,00	Upah dengan Sistem Tonase (Project) yaitu Rp. 180.000/Ton atau Rp. 800/Kg	Cuci Bahan Baku Oven (Jemur) Pendinginan Healer Ayak (Filter)	Rp. 300.000,00	Upah dengan Sistem Tonase (Project) yaitu Rp. 3000.000/Ton atau Rp. 300/Kg
3	Sortir Oven (Pengerangan) Packing	Rp. 1.500,00	Upah dengan Sistem Tonase (Project) yaitu Rp. 1.500/Kg	Sortir	Rp. 1.000,00	Upah dengan Sistem Tonase (Project) yaitu Rp. 1.000/Kg
4				Pengemasan Vacum Labeling Sealer Packing	Rp. 2.655,00	Upah dengan Sistem Tonase (Project) yaitu Rp. 2.655/Kg

The table above shows the volatility of the raw material price of candlenut kernels over the past six months, with UMKM reporting raw material purchases ranging from Rp 9,500 to Rp 12,000 over the past six months. In addition to fluctuating raw material prices, the table also explains the difference in labor costs between boiled candlenut production for the domestic market and peeled candlenut production for the export market.

Tabel 4

Results of Data Analysis Related to the Determination of Profit Margins between Boiled Candlenut Products (Domestic Market) and Peeled Candlenut Products (Export Market)

No	Nama Biaya	Harga	Jenis Produk			
			Kemiri Rebus (Domestik)		Kemiri Kupas (Ekspor)	
			Volume	Total Biaya (Kg)	Volume	Total Biaya (Kg)
1	Biaya Bahan Baku	10.833,00	2,86	30.951,43	4,08	44.252,45
2	Biaya Tenaga Kerja			2.300,00		3.955,00
3	Karung/Karton			80,00		640,00
4	Plastik Vacum	300,00			10,00	3.000,00
5	Labeling					890,00
6	Isolasi					120,00
7	listrik			100,00		1.000,00
Total Harga Pokok Produksi (HPP)/Kg			Rp 33.431,43		Rp 53.857,45	
Total Harga Jual (Kg)			Rp 35.000,00		Rp 71.000,00	
Margin Keuntungan/Kg			Rp 1.568,57		Rp 17.142,55	
Persentase Keuntungan /Kg			4,69%		31,83%	

The margin of peeled candlenut products for the export market in UMKM in Central Lombok is on average > 25% compared to the profit margin for boiled candlenut products for the domestic market. From the data above, on average, UMKM producing candlenuts for the export market get a margin or profit of 31.83% while UMKM producing candlenuts for the domestic market get a margin or profit of 4.69%. Based on the results of the independent T test where the domestic candlenut margin is 4.69% with a sample of 10 with a std of 3% while candlenut products for the export market have a margin of 31.83%, a sample size of 10, and a std of 5%, the t statistic results are -14.72 and a p-value of 3.24e-10 <0.001, this shows a significant difference between the margins of export and domestic products, UMKM in Central Lombok are more profitable if candlenut production is for the export market. This is because candlenut products for export require higher production costs than

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfishahrin

candlenuts for the domestic market. Furthermore, the export price is more stable than that of boiled candlenuts, making exports more profitable for UMKM in the long run, despite higher initial or production costs.

CONCLUSION

UMKM producing candlenuts for export have profit margins 5 to 8 times higher than those producing candlenuts for the local market. This study found that UMKM producing candlenuts for export have 25% higher profits than those producing candlenuts for the domestic market. Although they generate higher profits, UMKM producing candlenuts for the domestic market also face higher production costs and a longer production process. This study hopes that more UMKM will begin to focus on candlenut production for the export market, due to the more stable prices and higher profits. The local government must prioritize export potential by continuing to provide guidance and support to candlenut-producing UMKM with export potential. The government must also maintain stable raw material prices to facilitate candlenut-producing UMKM in determining selling prices. Hopefully, more UMKM will produce candlenuts for the export market, making Pancor Dao Village a foreign exchange hero village.

Author's Contribution

This research was conducted by two authors, each contributing according to their respective roles. The first author was responsible for developing the research idea, formulating the problem, and collecting and analyzing data. The second author was responsible for the literature review, developing the research instruments, and drafting and editing the manuscript. Both authors actively discussed the research at every stage and take full responsibility for the content of this article.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to the Directorate General of Higher Education, Research, and Technology (DIKTI) for the financial support provided through the Science and Technology Research Grant Program (Saintek) as well as the BIMA (Basis Informasi Manajemen Akademik) research grant scheme, which has significantly contributed to the successful completion of this research.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article, whether financial, commercial, or personal.

REFERENCES

Journal Article (Print Version)

- Anggara M, Utami SF, Rizqi RM. Inovasi Mesin Pengering Kemiri dan Manajemen Usaha Dalam Meningkatkan Nilai Ekonomi Kelompok Usaha Kemiri Kabupaten Sumbawa. In: Sendimas 2023 (Seminar Nasional Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat. 2023. p. 435–41.
- Haryadi W, Rachman R, Nisyah SA. Peran Usaha Mikro Kecil dan Menengah (UMKM) Dalam Meningkatkan Ekonomi Keluarga Petani Kemiri (Studi Kasus UD. Sumber Alam di Desa Batu Dulang Kec. Batu Lanteh Kab.Sumbawa). *J Ekon dan Bisnis*. 2019;7(3):232–42.
- Anggara M, Utami SF, Rizqi RM. Inovasi Mesin Pengering Kemiri dan Manajemen Usaha Dalam Meningkatkan Nilai Ekonomi Kelompok Usaha Kemiri Kabupaten Sumbawa. In: Sendimas 2023 (Seminar Nasional Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat. 2023. p. 435–41.
- Haryadi W, Rachman R, Nisyah SA. Peran Usaha Mikro Kecil dan Menengah (UMKM) Dalam Meningkatkan Ekonomi Keluarga Petani Kemiri (Studi Kasus UD. Sumber Alam di Desa Batu Dulang Kec. Batu Lanteh Kab.Sumbawa). *J Ekon dan Bisnis*. 2019;7(3):232–42.
- Puspita IL, Ariningrum H, Sariningsih E, Alansori A, Dewi TSW. Optimalisasi Desa Wisata Melalui Festival Wisata Kuliner Di Desa Kedungpari Jombang. *NEAR J Pengabdian Kpd Masy*. 2023;3(1):7–15.
- Dipya INT, Martadinata IPH. Penentuan Harga Pokok Produksi Dengan Metode Activitybased Costing Produk Minyak Kemiri Bakar Pada Umkm Oemah Uncle B Di Kabupaten Buleleng. *J Ilm Akunt dan Humanika*. 2024;14(1):43–54.
- Putri FR, Wijayanti, Runanto D. PENGARUH ORIENTASI KEWIRAUSAHAAN TERHADAP KINERJA UMKM DENGAN TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING (Studi

Publish by Radja Publika

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfisahrin

- pada UMKM Bibit Tanaman di Desa Karangduwur, Kecamatan Kemiri, Kabupaten Purworejo). Penambahan Natrium Benzoat Dan Kalium Sorbat Dan Kecepatan Pengadukan Sebagai Upaya Penghambatan Reaksi Inversi Pada Nira Tebu. 2024;6(5):131–43.
- Jundi F, Febriani J, Putri AD, Nurananda A, Diantari T, Tasya MA, et al. MENINGKATKAN KUALITAS PRODUK MASYARAKAT DALAM MENGOLAH MINYAK RAMBUT KEMIRI SEBAGAI SUMBER PENGHASILAN DI DESA TELAGAWARU. In: Prosiding Seminar Nasional Gelar Wicara. 2023. p. 805–8.
- Karimah Z, Lestari MG, Putri VM, Saputra FD, Nurhidayah FW, Ulva N. Pengembangan UMKM Melalui Peningkatan Pemasaran Produk Tempe Pak Kasman di Desa Jatiadi Kecamatan Gending Kabupaten Probolinggo. *Amaliah J Pengabdian Kpd Masy*. 2024;8(2):164–72.
- Anggara M, Utami SF, Rizqi RM. Inovasi Mesin Pengereng Kemiri dan Manajemen Usaha Dalam Meningkatkan Nilai Ekonomi Kelompok Usaha Kemiri Kabupaten Sumbawa. In: *Sendimas 2023 (Seminar Nasional Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat)*. 2023. p. 435–41.
- Haryadi W, Rachman R, Nisyah SA. Peran Usaha Mikro Kecil dan Menengah (UMKM) Dalam Meningkatkan Ekonomi Keluarga Petani Kemiri (Studi Kasus UD. Sumber Alam di Desa Batu Dulang Kec. Batu Lanteh Kab.Sumbawa). *J Ekon dan Bisnis*. 2019;7(3):232–42.
- Puspita IL, Ariningrum H, Sariningsih E, Alansori A, Dewi TSW. Optimalisasi Desa Wisata Melalui Festival Wisata Kuliner Di Desa Kedungpari Jombang. *NEAR J Pengabdian Kpd Masy*. 2023;3(1):7–15.
- Dipya INT, Martadinata IPH. Penentuan Harga Pokok Produksi Dengan Metode Activitybased Costing Produk Minyak Kemiri Bakar Pada Umkm Oemah Uncle B Di Kabupaten Buleleng. *J Ilm Akunt dan Humanika*. 2024;14(1):43–54.
- Putri FR, Wijayanti, Runanto D. PENGARUH ORIENTASI KEWIRAUSAHAAN TERHADAP KINERJA UMKM DENGAN TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT SEBAGAI VARIABEL INTERVENING (Studi pada UMKM Bibit Tanaman di Desa Karangduwur, Kecamatan Kemiri, Kabupaten Purworejo). Penambahan Natrium Benzoat Dan Kalium Sorbat Dan Kecepatan Pengadukan Sebagai Upaya Penghambatan Reaksi Inversi Pada Nira Tebu. 2024;6(5):131–43.
- Jundi F, Febriani J, Putri AD, Nurananda A, Diantari T, Tasya MA, et al. MENINGKATKAN KUALITAS PRODUK MASYARAKAT DALAM MENGOLAH MINYAK RAMBUT KEMIRI SEBAGAI SUMBER PENGHASILAN DI DESA TELAGAWARU. In: Prosiding Seminar Nasional Gelar Wicara. 2023. p. 805–8.
- Karimah Z, Lestari MG, Putri VM, Saputra FD, Nurhidayah FW, Ulva N. Pengembangan UMKM Melalui Peningkatan Pemasaran Produk Tempe Pak Kasman di Desa Jatiadi Kecamatan Gending Kabupaten Probolinggo. *Amaliah J Pengabdian Kpd Masy*. 2024;8(2):164–72.
- Sidin C, Indarti M. Pengaruh Jumlah Usaha Mikro Kecil Menengah Dan Jumlah Tenaga Kerja Umkm Terhadap Sumbangan Produk Domestik Bruto Umkm Periode Tahun 1997 – 2016. *J Manaj Kewirausahaan*. 2020;16(2):189.
- Yolanda C. Peran Usaha Mikro, Kecil Dan Menengah (UMKM) Dalam Pengembangan Ekonomi Indonesia. *J Manaj Dan Bisnis*. 2024;2(3):170–86.
- Hidayat D, **Hadi LAT**, Junaidin. Pengaruh Subsidi Pemerintah Terhadap Keberlanjutan Usaha Pedagang Kecil: Studi Pada Pasar Tradisional. *J Sci Mandalika*. 2024;5(11):450–6.
- Kencana, Surya. "Analisis Strategi Penetapan Harga SKM. CLOTHING." *Prosiding FRIMA (Festival Riset Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Akuntansi) 2 (2019): 1003-1011*.
- Ismail, Ismail. ANALISIS KOMPARATIF KEUNTUNGAN USAHATANI PINANG DAN KELAPA SAWIT DI KECAMATAN KUTA MAKMUR KABUPATEN ACEH UTARA. Diss. Universitas Malikussaleh, 2024.
- Primalasari, Ira, and Vera Octalia. "Analisis Komparasi Distribusi Keuntungan Penjualan Gabah dan Beras di Kabupaten Musi Rawas." *INSOLOGI: Jurnal Sains dan Teknologi* 4.6 (2025): 1636-1648.
- NADHIRAH, AULIA. "ANALISIS KEUNGGULAN KOMPARATIF USAHATANI UBI KAYU."
- Hasan, Nonce, and Rahmat Sabuhari. "Analisis potensi agribisnis pala (*Myristica fragrans houtt*)."*KINERJA: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Manajemen* 19.4 (2022): 862-868.
- Bayu Dien, Masroka, Sari Yunita, and Permata Sari Fifian. KOMPARATIF PENDAPATAN USAHATANI PADI ORGANIK TERSERTIFIKASI DAN NON ORGANIK DI KABUPATEN OKU TIMUR. Diss. Universitas Baturaja, 2024.
- Adiputra, Rahmad Dwi Cahyo, Masyhuri Machfudz, and Moch Noerhadi Sudjoni. "NALISIS PROFITABILITAS TANAMAN STROBERI PADA PT. AKAR LEBAT DI KOTA BATU." *Jurnal Sosial Ekonomi Pertanian*

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING PROFIT MARGINS FOR CANDLENUT PRODUCT SALES BETWEEN DOMESTIC AND EXPORT MARKETS FOR UMKM IN CENTRAL LOMBOK REGENCY

Lalu adiyatma Taopikul Hadi and Alfishahrin

dan Agribisnis 13.03 (2025).

Ningsih, Mutia Sahara. Standarisasi Penetapan Harga Komoditas Jagung Pipilan Dalam Perspektif Mabi' Pada Akad Jual Beli (Penelitian Di Kecamatan Deleng Pokhkisen Kabupaten Aceh Tenggara). Diss. UIN Ar-Raniry Fakultas Syariah dan Hukum, 2023.

Novrianti, Dian Puspita, Samsu Hilal, and Nezly Nurlia Putri. "ANALISIS PENENTUAN HARGA POKOK USAHA TANI BERAS PADA KECAMATAN WALANTAKA KOTA SERANG." *JURNAL REKAYASA SISTEM INDUSTRI* 8.1 (2022): 41-45.

Rengga, Andreas, Paulus Juru, and Yosef Tonce. "ANALISIS PERBEDAAN HARGA JUAL KAKAO ASALAN DAN KAKAO SERTIFIKASI PADA PT. CELEBES MAKMUR ABADI MAUMERE." *Jurnal Projemen UNIPA* 10.1 (2023): 49-61.

Magfiroh, Niswatul, and Muh Syarif. "Pengaruh Rantai Distribusi Terhadap Penetapan Harga Jual Pada Komoditas Jagung Di Kabupaten Pamekasan." *Innovative: Journal Of Social Science Research* 3.6 (2023): 9313-9327.